

Strategies for the sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province

Gan Lin^{1,2*}, Phisanu Bangkheow¹, Phatchareephorn Bangkheow¹ and Narongwat Mingmit¹

¹Bansomdejchaopraya Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand.

²College of Information Engineering, Shaanxi Fashion Engineering University, Shaanxi, China.

Accepted 19 February, 2026

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to investigate the current and desired conditions, develop strategies, and evaluate the feasibility and adaptability of sustainable education development for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province. Using stratified random sampling, 384 participants—including teachers, caregivers, and community workers—completed a validated questionnaire (IOC = 0.80–1.00; Cronbach's α = 0.923), supplemented by in-depth interviews, focus groups, and expert evaluations involving 25 experts. Analysis combined quantitative methods (percentages, means, standard deviations, modified Priority Needs Index [PNI]) with qualitative content analysis. Results revealed significant gaps across four core dimensions: Individual Characteristics, School Education Support, Family-Social Factors, and Government Policy and Funding Support. The highest priorities identified via PNI were Family-Social Factors (PNI = 0.615) and Government Policy and Funding Support (PNI = 0.600). Based on these findings, a strategic framework with a clear vision, mission, and objectives was developed, operationalized through four targeted pathways aligned with each dimension. Expert evaluation confirmed the strategies' strong feasibility ($X(\bar{)} = 4.42$) and adaptability ($X(\bar{)} = 4.39$), affirming their applicability to promoting sustainable education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province.

Keywords: Strategies, sustainable development, education for left-behind children, Shaanxi Province.

*Corresponding author. E-mail: ganlin606@gmail.com. Tel: 096-858-8746.

INTRODUCTION

Introduce the problem

In China, and particularly in Shaanxi Province, the education of left-behind children (LBCs)—defined as those who remain in their home communities while one or both parents migrate for employment—has emerged as a pressing concern (Duan et al., 2013; Zhou and Duan, 2006). This phenomenon is driven by a complex interplay of social, economic, and emotional challenges that disproportionately affect LBCs (Gao et al., 2019; Ye and Pan, 2011). Often placed under the care of extended family members or other guardians, these children are at heightened risk of educational disruption, psychological stress, and inadequate developmental support (Liang and

Chen, 2007; Meng and Yamauchi, 2017). Compounding these issues are disparities in educational resource allocation and diminished community engagement (OECD, 2018; Wang and Guan, 2025), which together constitute formidable obstacles to both academic achievement and holistic well-being.

Given the distinctive and multifaceted challenges confronting left-behind children (LBCs), bridging the gaps in their educational development is essential not only for securing their immediate academic outcomes but also for facilitating their long-term socioeconomic inclusion. This study aims to examine the current status of educational provision for LBCs in Shaanxi Province and to develop an integrated framework for sustainable educational

advancement that comprehensively addresses their academic, psychological, and social needs.

Research questions

1. What are the current and desired conditions for sustainable development of education for left-behind children of Shaanxi Province?
2. What were the sustainable development strategies for the education of left-behind children of Shaanxi?
3. What was the level of feasibility and adaptability of strategies for sustainable development of education for Left-behind Children in Shaanxi Province?

Research objectives

1. To study the current and desired conditions for sustainable development of education for left-behind children of Shaanxi Province.
2. To develop strategies for the sustainable development of education for left-behind children of Shaanxi Province.
3. To evaluate the feasibility and adaptability of strategies for the sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province.

Research scope

This study was structured into three sequential phases to systematically achieve the research objectives.

Phase 1: Studying the current and desired conditions for sustainable development of education for left-behind children of Shaanxi Province.

Population and the sample group

1. Population

In Shaanxi Province, there are approximately 286,000 left-behind children distributed across 107 counties and districts.

2. The Sample Group

The sample group consisted of 384 left-behind children, who were selected from 10 primary and secondary schools across three regions in Shaanxi Province.

3. 10 purposively selected experts—including experienced teachers and administrators, education policymakers, researchers, and social workers with direct involvement in supporting left-behind children—participated in interviews to assess current conditions.

Phase 2: Development of strategies for the sustainable development of education for left-behind children of Shaanxi Province

To develop strategies for the sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province, a focus group was convened with 10 experts specializing in relevant fields.

Phase 3: Evaluation of the feasibility and adaptability of strategies for sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province

A panel of 5 experts evaluated the feasibility and adaptability of the strategies for sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province.

Variables

Independent variable

Strategy, sustainable development, education for left-behind children, Shaanxi Province.

Dependent variable

The feasibility and adaptability of the strategies for sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province.

Content

1. The current and desired states of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province were examined through questionnaires, interviews, and focus groups, with key gaps analyzed across four dimensions—individual characteristics, school education support, family-social networks, and government policy and funding—to identify priority needs and understand barriers and enablers to educational sustainability.

2. Strategic directions were formulated using SWOT and TOWS analyses to address challenges in each dimension, resulting in the development of context-specific strategies aimed at promoting sustainable education for left-behind children.

3. The proposed strategies were evaluated by five experts for feasibility and adaptability, refined based on feedback to ensure practicality and relevance, and subsequently translated into policy recommendations and practical guidelines to support effective implementation and long-term sustainability of educational interventions.

Advantage

1. For left-behind children, this study develops context-specific, sustainable educational strategies to enhance their psychological resilience, learning motivation, and overall well-being, empowering them through supportive environments, strengthened psychosocial support, and improved family-school collaboration to achieve better academic engagement, mental health, and future readiness.
2. For teachers, the research provides deeper insights into the unique challenges of left-behind children, enabling more targeted and empathetic teaching practices, reducing emotional burdens, and strengthening teacher-student relationships to improve teaching quality and professional fulfillment.
3. For schools and communities, the study offers a structured framework for sustainable educational management that optimizes governance and resources, cultivates equitable and nurturing environments, and enhances schools' roles in community development, making them key centers for student growth, engagement, and educational equity in line with Shaanxi's regional development goals.

Definition subsections

1. Strategy refers to a systematic, forward-looking approach that aligns internal resources with external conditions to achieve long-term goals such as sustainability and resilience (Wehrich, 1982). It provides a cohesive framework for coordinated action toward a shared vision.
2. Sustainable development in education for left-behind children goes beyond service continuity; it entails building inclusive, resilient, and culturally anchored educational ecosystems that promote lasting well-being, capability enhancement, and intergenerational equity.
3. Education for left-behind children is a multidimensional effort addressing academic, emotional, and social challenges caused by parental migration (Wang and Mao, 2018; Xie and Zhang, 2023). It integrates pedagogical, institutional, and community supports to foster equitable opportunities, resilience, and holistic development.
4. Shaanxi Province exhibits pronounced geographic and socioeconomic disparities, with rural and remote areas facing significant educational deficits (Wang and Guan, 2025). Its unique context—shaped by migration, inequality, and cultural diversity—necessitates targeted, adaptable strategies that respond to the complex realities of left-behind children (Bai et al., 2018).

Conceptual framework

Figure 1. Conceptual framework.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design

In order to conduct strategic research on strategies for the sustainable development of education for left-behind children, the research was a mixed-methods research that operated in 3 phases:

Phases 1. Study of Current and Desired Conditions: Studying the current and desired conditions for sustainable development of education for left-behind children of Shaanxi Province.

Phases 2. Strategy Development: Development of strategies for the sustainable development of education for left-behind children of Shaanxi Province.

Phases 3. Strategy Evaluation: Evaluation of the feasibility and adaptability of strategies for sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province.

Participants

Sample size

This study focused on the sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province, which has an estimated 286,000 such children across 107 counties, primarily in Northern, Southern, and Central Shaanxi (Zhou and Duan, 2006; Duan et al., 2013). Ten primary and secondary schools from urban, rural, and mountainous areas in these regions were selected for data collection. Following Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) sampling guidelines, 384 left-behind children were randomly chosen for questionnaire surveys, along with their guardians, homeroom teachers, and school administrators, ensuring a representative sample in terms of gender, age, geography, and family background.

Through purposive sampling, 10 individuals related to left-behind children were selected from 10 schools as interviewees and participants in focus groups.

Sampling procedures

This questionnaire is designed based on the investigation of the current situation and influencing factors of the sustainable development of left-behind children's education in Shaanxi Province. The influencing factors are divided into four levels, including: Individual Characteristics, School Education Support, Family Social Factors, and Government Policy and Funding Support. The questionnaires were collected through WeChat and the online platform Questionnaire Star, and the data analysis was conducted using the mean and standard deviation to obtain the results.

This study adopted a specially designed interview outline and presented the information provided by the respondents through structured interviews. The interviewees must meet the following conditions: a total of 10 people, with a deputy senior or higher professional title, and having more than 10 years of experience in left-behind children's education.

Finally, the researchers invited five experts to evaluate the applicability and feasibility of the strategies formed for the sustainable development of left-behind children's education in Shaanxi Province. These experts all have a deputy senior or higher professional title and many years of educational work experience.

Research instruments

This study employed a set of composite research tools to collect data from multiple dimensions, ensuring the comprehensiveness and validity of the research findings. The tool combination includes: 1) a rating scale questionnaire for assessing the current and expected status of sustainable education development for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province; 2) a semi-structured interview guide for collecting qualitative data; 3) a strategy evaluation form developed based on the Likert scale for expert validity testing. The reliability of the questionnaire was verified, with a Cronbach's α coefficient of 0.932, indicating good internal consistency and reliable measurement results.

Data collection

Data were collected in three phases. Quantitative data were gathered via the distributed questionnaire, while qualitative data were obtained through semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions. Finally, the developed strategy was submitted to five experts for validation regarding its feasibility and adaptability.

Data analysis

Data analysis was conducted using a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods. Firstly, descriptive statistics (percentages, means, and standard deviations) were employed to analyze the current and expected status of sustainable education development for left-behind children. To further identify the most critical areas requiring attention, a Priority Needs Index (PNI) was calculated (English and Kaufman, 1975; Witkin and Altschuld, 1995; Fortner and Corney, 2002). Secondly, for strategy formulation, the research utilized the SWOT analysis and TOWS matrix analysis framework to systematically sort out internal and external factors and generate targeted

strategies (Weihrich, 1982). Additionally, qualitative content analysis was performed on the records of interviews and focus group discussions to extract key themes relevant to strategy design and validation, ensuring that the strategy recommendations were grounded in the in-depth insights from field research.

Research process

This study employed a mixed-methods design carried out

in three sequential phases aligned with its core objectives: first, assessing the current and desired conditions for sustainable education development among left-behind children in Shaanxi Province; second, formulating targeted strategies based on the findings; and third, evaluating the feasibility and adaptability of those strategies. Each phase served as empirical evidence for its corresponding research goal, ensuring a rigorous and context-sensitive approach that combined academic depth with practical relevance, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Research methodology.

RESULTS

The research on strategies for sustainable development of

education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province aims to achieve the following objectives: 1) To study the current and desired conditions for sustainable development of

education for left-behind children of Shaanxi Province. 2) To develop strategies for the sustainable development of education for left-behind children of Shaanxi Province. 3) To evaluate the feasibility and adaptability of strategies for the sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province. The details are shown in Table 1.

Problems and influencing factors in the process of improving sustainable development strategies for left-behind children's education in Shaanxi Province

According to the data in Table 1, the current conditions of

sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province, as reflected by the average score of the four dimensions, are at a moderately low level (Mean = 2.30, S.D. = 0.88). Among the dimensions, the mean values from highest to lowest are: School Education Support (Mean = 2.42, S.D. = 0.89), Individual Characteristics (Mean = 2.35, S.D. = 0.81), Government Policy and Funding Support (Mean = 2.25, S.D. = 0.86), and Family Social Factors (Mean = 2.18, S.D. = 0.94). This pattern indicates that educational development for left-behind children in the province remains in need of substantial enhancement across all areas (Fortner and Corney, 2002).

Table 1. Analysis of the current conditions and expected conditions of the sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province.

The sustainable development of education for left-behind children	Current conditions (D)		Desired conditions (I)		PNImodified (I-D)/D	Rank
	\bar{X}	S.D.	\bar{X}	S.D.		
1. Individual characteristics	2.35	0.81	3.28	0.72	0.396	4
2. School education support	2.42	0.89	3.45	0.75	0.426	3
3. Family social factors	2.18	0.94	3.52	0.68	0.615	1
4. Government policy and funding support	2.25	0.86	3.60	0.70	0.600	2
Total	2.30	0.88	3.46	0.71	0.487	

SWOT and TOWS Matrix of total: Individual characteristics, school education support, family social factors, government policy and funding support

Integrating the SWOT findings across all four dimensions provides a comprehensive view of the systemic strengths,

weaknesses, opportunities, and threats influencing the sustainable education of left-behind children, and serves as the basis for coordinated cross-dimensional strategies (Wehrich, 1982). The findings from this assessment are detailed in Table 2.

Table 2. Results of SWOT and TOWS Matrix Analysis of SWOT and TOWS matrix of total: individual characteristics, school education support, family social factors, government policy and funding support.

S	W
S1 Individual Characteristics – Basic self-care ability and growing independence	W1 School Education Support – Insufficient extracurricular support and tutoring services
S2 School Education Support – Reasonable school curriculum design and resource allocation	W2 Family-Social Factors – Insufficient parental involvement and low communication frequency
S3 Family-Social Factors – Effective community-level implementation of educational support policies	W3 Government Policy and Funding Support – Insufficient adequacy of financial support for educational programs
S4 Government Policy and Funding Support – Relatively high public awareness and understanding of relevant policies	W4 Government Policy and Funding Support – Limited clarity and accessibility of policies for left-behind children

Table 2. Continued.

<p>O</p> <p>O1 School Education Support – Expansion of digital teaching resources and smart campus infrastructure</p> <p>O2 Family-Social Factors – Increased public awareness and mobilization of nongovernmental organizations</p> <p>O3 Government Policy and Funding Support – National emphasis on inclusive education and poverty alleviation</p> <p>O4 Government Policy and Funding Support – Increasing public-private partnerships expanding support channels</p>	<p>T</p> <p>T1 Family-Social Factors – Economic disparity across regions limiting family support capacity</p> <p>T2 School Education Support – Teacher shortages and high turnover in remote areas</p> <p>T3 Government Policy and Funding Support – Bureaucratic inefficiencies slowing policy implementation</p> <p>T4 Family-Social Factors – Social stigma and insufficient recognition of left-behind children</p>
---	---

SWOT and PEST analysis of total: Individual characteristics, school education support, family social factors, government policy and funding support

Following the comprehensive TOWS analysis of the four dimensions individually and in total, this section introduces the PEST (Political, Economic, Social, Technological) framework to examine the broader external environment (Wehrich, 1982). The integration of SWOT and PEST aims to provide a holistic understanding of the strategic conditions for the sustainable education of left-behind

children in Shaanxi Province, identifying how macro-environmental factors influence the internal strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. This combined approach also highlights potential leverage points where policy alignment, economic investment, social mobilization, and technological innovation can reinforce targeted interventions. Such an integrated view supports the formulation of strategies that are both context-sensitive and future-ready, ensuring coordinated action across multiple levels. The details are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. SWOT and PEST analysis of total: Individual characteristics, school education support, family social factors, government policy and funding support.

<p>S</p> <p>S1 Individual Characteristics – Basic self-care ability and growing independence</p> <p>S2 School Education Support – Reasonable school curriculum design and resource allocation</p> <p>S3 Family-Social Factors – Effective community-level implementation of educational support policies</p> <p>S4 Government Policy and Funding Support – Relatively high public awareness and understanding of relevant policies</p>	<p>W</p> <p>W1 School Education Support – Insufficient extracurricular support and tutoring services</p> <p>W2 Family-Social Factors – Insufficient parental involvement and low communication frequency</p> <p>W3 Government Policy and Funding Support – Insufficient adequacy of financial support for educational programs</p> <p>W4 Government Policy and Funding Support – Limited clarity and accessibility of policies for left-behind children</p>
<p>O</p> <p>O1 National emphasis on inclusive education and poverty alleviation</p> <p>O2 Expansion of digital teaching resources and smart campus infrastructure</p> <p>O3 Increased public awareness and mobilization of nongovernmental organizations</p> <p>O4 Increasing public-private partnerships expanding support channels</p>	<p>T</p> <p>T1 Economic disparity across regions limiting family support capacity</p> <p>T2 Social stigma and insufficient recognition of left-behind children</p> <p>T3 Bureaucratic inefficiencies slowing policy implementation & fiscal fluctuations affecting sustainability</p> <p>T4 Teacher shortages and high turnover in remote areas</p>

Based on the results of the second phase of the questionnaire survey and the in-depth content of the third

phase of expert interviews, a comprehensive SWOT analysis was conducted on the gathered data. This

analysis reveals that the sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province faces multifaceted challenges and opportunities, necessitating enhancement in four critical and interconnected domains: Individual Characteristics, School Education Support, Family-Social Factors, and Government Policy and Funding Support. Recognizing that these dimensions are not isolated but mutually reinforcing, this study proposes a holistic set of sustainable development strategies (Gao et al., 2022; He et al., 2022). These strategies are designed to address the core issues identified, fostering a synergistic effect to comprehensively improve the educational ecosystem for left-behind children. Specifically, the proposed framework encompasses four primary strategic dimensions with a total of 62 specific, actionable measures, as systematically presented in Table 4. This integrated approach aims not

only to mitigate existing deficiencies but also to build long-term resilience within the system. The details are shown in Table 4.

According to Table 4, this is a comprehensive overview of strategies aimed at enhancing the educational support system for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province. Each strategy is linked to a specific set of concrete measures, reflecting a structured approach to achieving targeted outcomes in different domains. The components of these strategies cover a broad range of priority areas, including enhancing Individual Characteristics, enhancing School Education Support, enhancing Family-Social Factors, and enhancing Government Policy and Funding Support. Together, they form an integrated framework designed to address the multifaceted challenges identified in the SWOT analysis and to foster sustainable development of education for left-behind children.

Table 4. List of sustainable development strategies for education of left-behind children in Shaanxi Province.

No.	Aspects of strategies	Numbers of measures
1	Strategies for enhancing individual characteristics	18
2	Strategies for enhancing school education support	20
3	Strategies for enhancing family-social factors	16
4	Strategies for enhancing government policy and funding support	8
Total	4 strategies	62

The strategy for enhancing individual characteristics comprises 18 measures, aimed at strengthening the intrinsic capacities of left-behind children in Shaanxi Province (Wang and Mao, 2018; Xie and Zhang, 2023). These measures may involve initiatives such as resilience-oriented life skills training, multi-dimensional psychological quality development camps, independent learning modules, and personalized education plans, targeting emotional well-being, self-management, and cognitive growth. Their significance lies in cultivating children's motivation, resilience, and autonomy, enabling them to overcome adversity and engage actively in learning, thus forming a solid foundation for long-term personal and academic success. By embedding these measures into daily schooling and out-of-school programs, children can progressively internalize adaptive skills that help them navigate uncertainty and sustain effort even without constant parental presence. Moreover, fostering self-awareness and goal-setting abilities empowers them to take ownership of their learning pathways, which is essential for bridging gaps caused by fragmented home support.

The strategy for improving the school education and support environment consists of 20 measures, intended to

transform schools into comprehensive hubs that nurture and protect left-behind children (Liu and Villa, 2020; Zhao et al., 2014). These measures may include establishing inclusive school cultures, implementing school-based mental health programs, developing life skills curricula, setting up after-school tutoring centers, and launching school social worker stations, alongside strengthening teacher training and inter-school resource sharing (Gao et al., 2022). They are meaningful because they ensure that schools provide not only academic instruction but also holistic psychosocial support, safety, and a sense of belonging, which are vital for mitigating the vulnerabilities these children face. This environment helps counteract the instability often associated with parental absence by offering consistent relationships with educators and peers who can act as protective figures. In addition, integrated support mechanisms enable early identification of learning or emotional difficulties, allowing timely interventions that prevent escalation and promote steady academic and social progress.

The strategy for optimizing family and social external factors includes 16 measures, designed to weave a stronger support network around left-behind children by engaging families and communities (Ye and Pan, 2011;

Ren and Treiman, 2016). These measures may involve creating family-school-community collaboration platforms, organizing parental involvement programs, opening access to community resources, introducing professional social workers, and launching public awareness campaigns to reduce stigma. Their value stems from mobilizing community assets and social capital, fostering inclusive and caring environments, and bridging gaps caused by physical separation from parents, thereby enhancing children's social integration and emotional security. Such networks also facilitate two-way communication that keeps caregivers informed and engaged despite geographical distance, reinforcing their sense of responsibility and connection to the child's education. When communities collectively affirm the worth of these children, it reduces marginalization and cultivates an atmosphere where mutual assistance becomes a sustainable norm.

The strategy for optimizing government policy and funding support encompasses 8 measures, focused on

establishing systemic enablers for sustainable educational development (Liang and Chen, 2007; Bai et al., 2018). These measures may include enacting specialized local regulations, forming multi-departmental coordinating committees, optimizing financial allocation formulas with weighted funding for left-behind children, and instituting data platforms and third-party evaluation mechanisms (OECD, 2018). They are critical because they provide stable policy direction, equitable resource distribution, and effective oversight, ensuring that the other three strategy dimensions can be implemented consistently and scaled across regions. A coherent policy framework also aligns diverse stakeholders behind shared objectives, reducing duplication of effort and encouraging evidence-based adjustments over time. With transparent monitoring and accountability mechanisms in place, resources are less likely to be diverted, and successful pilot initiatives can be replicated efficiently, strengthening long-term impact across varied local contexts. The details are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. An assessment and analysis of the feasibility and adaptability of sustainable development strategies for the education of left-behind children in Shaanxi Province.

Strategies for the sustainable development of education for left-behind children	\bar{X}	Feasibility		\bar{X}	Adaptability	
		S.D.	Result		S.D.	Result
1. Strategies for enhancing individual characteristics	4.40	0.38	High	4.55	0.35	High
2. Strategies for enhancing school education support	4.45	0.36	High	4.50	0.38	High
3. Strategies for enhancing family-social factors	4.50	0.34	High	4.45	0.36	High
4. Strategies for enhancing government policy and funding support	4.85	0.28	Highest	4.80	0.25	Highest
Total	4.55	0.34	High	4.57	0.33	High

Results of evaluation of the feasibility and of strategies for sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province.

To ensure the proposed strategies were both actionable and contextually appropriate, a panel of five experts conducted a comprehensive evaluation of their feasibility and adaptability. The assessment was based on a 5-point Likert scale, with particular attention to the potential for real-world implementation and alignment with the specific social, economic, and educational conditions of Shaanxi Province. The results of this expert appraisal are summarized in Table 5.

According to Table 5, the mean adaptability scores of the four strategic dimensions range from 4.45 to 4.80, and the mean feasibility scores range from 4.40 to 4.85, all falling within the high to highest level. This indicates that the

research strategies possess strong feasibility and adaptability for promoting the sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province. These scores reflect a high degree of consensus among stakeholders, underscoring the practical viability and contextual appropriateness of the proposed strategies.

These strategies collectively form an integrated, multi-dimensional framework that addresses Individual Characteristics, School Education Support, Family-Social Factors, and Government Policy and Funding Support—the 4 strategic domains identified through SWOT analysis and expert consultation. By aligning targeted measures across these interconnected areas, the framework aims to strengthen the educational ecosystem and ensure the sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province. The details are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Strategy system framework.

CONCLUSION

This study, research on the strategies for the sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province, was conducted using a mixed-methods approach, implemented in three phases (Krejcie and Morgan, 1970; Weihrich, 1982; English and Kaufman, 1975). The main findings are as follows: 1) Studying the current and desired conditions for sustainable development of education for left-behind children of Shaanxi Province. 2) Development of strategies for the sustainable development of education for left-behind children of Shaanxi Province. 3) Evaluation of the feasibility and adaptability of strategies for sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province.

The proposed framework comprises four interlinked strategies designed to address the multi-level determinants of educational sustainability for left-behind children. 1) At the individual level, the first strategy promotes self-determination, emotional regulation, and proactive learning through experiential activities, reflective practice, and peer support, thereby enhancing intrinsic motivation, psychological resilience, and goal-setting capacity. 2) The second strategy strengthens school-level support by creating inclusive, responsive environments; improving teacher competence; integrating targeted instruction and welfare services; and developing school—family—community networks, digital communication tools, and mentorship systems. 3) The third strategy focuses on expanding family, community, and social support by mobilizing social capital, enhancing guardians' parenting skills, and establishing collaborative platforms involving

professional social workers and public awareness campaigns. 4) The fourth strategy targets the policy and funding dimension, advocating for clear regulatory frameworks, optimized fiscal allocation, cross-sector coordination, and transparent monitoring mechanisms to ensure sustainable, equitable, and accountable delivery of educational resources. Together, these strategies form a comprehensive, multi-tiered approach to fostering the academic success and holistic well-being of LBCs in Shaanxi Province.

REFERENCES

- Bai, N., Zhang, X., Liu, C., Shi, Y., Di, X., & Rozelle, S. (2018). The impact of parental migration on left-behind children's educational outcomes: Evidence from rural China. *China Economic Review*, 51, 89–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chieco.2018.04.001>
- Duan, C., Lü, L., Guo, J., & Wang, Z. (2013). *Survival and development of left-behind children in China: Based on the sixth census data*. Beijing: Social Sciences Academic Press.
- English, F. W., & Kaufman, R. A. (1975). *Needs assessment: A focus on curriculum development*. Washington, DC: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Fortner, R. W., & Corney, P. (2002). The status of environmental education in Ohio elementary schools: A follow-up study. *Journal of Environmental Education*, 33(2), 12–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00958960209601048>
- Gao, Y., Li, L., Kim, H., Congdon, N., Lau, J., & Griffiths, S. (2019). The impact of parental migration on psychological wellbeing and learning outcomes of left-behind children in China. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(15), 8085. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18158085>
- Gao, Y., Li, L., Zhang, Y., & Zou, H. (2022). Addressing educational barriers faced by left-behind children in rural China: A mixed-methods study. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 6(8), 45–62.
- He, X., Zhang, R., & Zhu, B. (2022). A prospective study on resilience among children with different migrant and left-behind trajectories. *Child*

- Indicators Research, 15(6), 2065–2091. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12187-022-09945-1>
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30(3), 607–610. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001316447003000308>
- Liang, Z., & Chen, Y. P. (2007). The educational consequences of migration for children in China. *Social Science Research*, 36(1), 28–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2006.01.005>
- Liu, H., & Villa, L. (2020). School boarding and psychosocial development of rural left-behind children in China. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 116, 105192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chilyouth.2020.105192>
- Meng, X., & Yamauchi, C. (2017). Children of migrants: The impact of parental migration on their children's education and health outcomes. *Demography*, 54(5), 1757–1778. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13524-017-0613-3>
- OECD. (2018). *Innovation, agricultural productivity and sustainability in China*. Paris: OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264085299-en>
- Ren, Y., & Treiman, D. J. (2016). Living arrangements and educational outcomes of children in rural China. *Social Science Research*, 60, 222–237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2016.05.006>
- Rundh, B. (2016). The role of packaging in marketing communications: A case study of IKEA. *Journal of Business and Retail Management Research*, 10(3), 65–76.
- psychiatric nursing framework. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 13, 1709606. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2025.1709606>
- Zhao, X., Chen, J., & Murray, S. (2014). Parental migration and rural left-behind children's human capital development in China. *China Agricultural Economic Review*, 6(4), 696–711. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CAER-02-2014-0016>
- Zhou, C., & Duan, C. (2006). *Research on left-behind children in China*. Beijing: Population Research Institute, Chinese Academy of Social Sciences.
- Zhou, C., et al. (2015). The left-behind children in China: A meta-analysis of the prevalence and mental health status. *Asia Pacific Journal of Public Health*, 27(2), 1581–1592. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1010539515597620>
- Wang, F., & Mao, Y. (2018). Parental migration and psychological resilience of rural left-behind children in China: The role of parent-child communication. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 6, 284. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2018.00284>
- Wang, L., & Geng, J. (2019). Family instability and child development: Evidence from rural China. *China Economic Review*, 55, 143–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chieco.2019.02.001>
- Wehrich, H. (1982). The TOWS matrix—A tool for situational analysis. *Long Range Planning*, 15(2), 54–66. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0024-6301\(82\)90195-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0024-6301(82)90195-1)
- Witkin, B. R., & Altschuld, J. W. (1995). *Planning and conducting needs assessments: A practical guide*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.
- Xie, L., & Zhang, Y. (2023). Psychological resilience among left-behind children in a rural area of Eastern China. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(15), 5388. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17155388>
- Ye, J., & Pan, L. (2011). Differentiated childhoods: Impacts of rural labor migration on left-behind children in China. *Journal of Peasant Studies*, 38(2), 355–377. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03066150.2011.559009>
- Zhang, Y., & Chen, Y. (2024). Family-centered mental health care for left-behind children in Chinese ethnic minority concentrated areas: A

Citation: Lin, G., Bangkheow, P., Bangkheow, P., and Mingmit, N. (2026). Strategies for the sustainable development of education for left-behind children in Shaanxi Province. *African Educational Research Journal*, 14(1), 250-260.
